

European Commission Consultation on the Draft Delegation Regulation supplementing Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 on data access provided for in the Digital Services Act

**Contribution of the Centre for Internet and Society, CNRS and
the Research Network on Internet, AI and Society CNRS**

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Contributing institution:

The Center for Internet and Society (CIS) is a CNRS research center combining a research unit (UPR 2000) created in 2019, and the Internet, AI and Society (GDR 2091) Research Network, founded in 2020.

At the intersection of sociology, law, history, economics, political science, information and communication sciences, computer and engineering sciences, the CIS intends to build independent and interdisciplinary research and expertise. The CIS' research endeavours to contribute to enlightening the major technical controversies and the definition of contemporary policies related to the digital, to the internet, and more broadly to informatics. As part of its activities, CIS is also a laboratory for the elaboration and promotion of good practices in digital

¹ This report is a collective synthesis of individual feedback from each contributor. The contributors would also like to thank Nicolas Ancaux and Oana Goga for insightful discussions.

technology for science (collaborative tools, digital methods of survey, analysis and visualization of data, communication strategy, participatory research).

The Research Network on Internet, AI and Society (GDR 2091 Internet IA et Société) brings together more than 750 researchers from universities, research institutions, public and private institutions from France and abroad. Organised in 18 working groups, research conducted by this interdisciplinary research network covers a broad range of topics related to the societal and political dimension of digital technologies, such as Internet governance, the mitigation of the environmental impacts of IT, digital democracy, AI and arts, and digital commons. Publications include a report for the STOA Panel of the European Parliament on Internet fragmentation², a report written by Fing (a think-tank) on 5G policy³, publications on digital health⁴ and others on Internet standardisation and governance⁵.

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² Clément Perarnaud, Julien Rossi, Francesca Musiani and Lucien Castex, "Splinternets': Addressing the renewed debate on internet fragmentation' (Report for the Panel for the Future of Science and Technology), June 2022, doi:10.2861/183513

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_STU\(2022\)729530](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_STU(2022)729530)

³ Fondation Internet Nouvelle Génération and GDR 2091 Internet, IA et Société, "Débats 5G – Quels apports de la recherche ?", December 2020,

<https://cis.cnrs.fr/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/FING-5G-GDR-V1.pdf>

⁴ Cristina Lindenmeyer et Marie-Pia d'Ortho (dir.), *Santé connectée*, CNRS Éditions, coll. « Les Essentiels d'Hermès », 2020, 216 p.

⁵ Julien Rossi, Francesca Musiani et Lucien Castex (coord.), *Quand la gouvernance d'Internet fait controverse. Études, méthodes, analyses*, numéro spécial 132-133, Terminal, mars 2022. Texte intégral [[10.4000/terminal.8203](https://doi.org/10.4000/terminal.8203)]

Introduction

The Centre for Internet and Society and the Research Network on Internet, AI and Society of CNRS welcome the consultation by the European Commission on the 'Draft Delegated Regulation supplementing Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council by laying down the technical conditions and procedures under which providers of very large online platforms and of very large online search engines are to share data pursuant to Article 40 of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065.' (Draft Regulations)

Article 40 of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 ('DSA') is an important provision in enabling open research on the role of online platforms and search engines in the digital society, by allowing researchers to obtain data held by such actors. As we noted in our responses to the previous consultation on this topic conducted by the European Commission in 2023, platforms have historically restricted access to data even for public interest research purposes.⁶ Researchers often rely on voluntary data donations or data access programs by platforms, the scope of which are largely determined by platforms themselves.⁷ As a result, a regulatory framework for data access is significant in monitoring compliance by platforms with laws such as the DSA as well as enabling transparency into the role and activities of platforms in shaping digital society.⁸

The Draft Regulations incorporate some elements of our responses to the previous consultation. To ensure that the Draft Regulations enable the full realisation of the objectives of Articles 40(1) and 40(4) of the DSA, we propose the following amendments to the provisions of the Draft Regulation.

Our proposed amendments are based on two objectives. *First*, we seek to reflect certain common/probable research practices in the Draft Regulations. For instance, one set of amendments concern changes to principal researchers during the subsistence of a research project. Another set of amendments create the possibility for researchers to provide documentation from the operator of a secure processing environment *after* a reasoned request has been accepted by the data provider. This is because funders are likely to require proof that the reasoned request will be acted on before making the necessary funds available to the principal researchers for purchase of access to the secure processing environment.

⁶ Contribution of the Research Network on Internet, AI and Society CNRS, Responses to the consultation on Delegated Regulation on data access provided for in the Digital Services Act, May 31, 2023, https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13817-Delegated-Regulation-on-data-access-provided-for-in-the-Digital-Services-Act/F3423885_en

⁷ See for e.g., Stefan Verhulst and David Sangokoya, 'Mapping the Next Frontier of Open Data: Corporate Data Sharing' (*Medium*, 15 January 2015), <https://medium.com/internet-monitor-2014-data-and-privacy/mapping-the-next-frontier-of-open-data-corporate-data-sharing-73b2143878d2>

⁸ See for e.g., Paddy Leerssen, 'Outside the Black Box' 4(2) (2024) *Weizenbaum Journal of the Digital Society*.

Second, we seek to make the Draft Regulations more precise. This includes changes to specify time periods for actions, changes to the mediation process to ensure due process, and other changes to ensure that the Draft Regulations do not conflict with or go beyond the scope of Article 40 of the DSA (part of the principles of delegation of powers set down in Article 290 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union).

We conclude our contribution with some general remarks on Article 40 of the DSA.

Proposed amendments

- Visa

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Having regard to the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, Having regard to Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (2), and in particular Article 40(13) thereof,</p>	<p>THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Having regard to the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, Having regard to the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, and in particular Articles 7, 8 and 13 thereof, Having regard to Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (2), and in particular Article 40(13) thereof,</p>

Justification

It must be remembered that access to data processed by very large online platforms must be done in a way that complies with fundamental rights defined in the Charter. This includes the right to privacy and data protection, but also academic freedom.

- Recital 28

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>Where the data provided to the vetted researchers include personal data, the data provider should make use of the possibilities offered by Regulation (EU) 2016/679. In particular, Article 40(4) of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 creates a legal obligation in the sense of Article 6(1), point (c) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 for any processing of personal data necessary for the data provider to provide access to the data specified in the reasoned request.</p>	<p>Where the data provided to the vetted researchers include personal data, the data provider should make use of the possibilities offered by Regulation (EU) 2016/679. In particular, Article 40(4) of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 creates a legal obligation in the sense of Article 6(1), point (c) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 for any processing of personal data necessary for the data provider to provide access to the data specified in the reasoned request.</p>

Where special categories of personal data within the meaning of Article 9 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 are to be processed, the data provider should demonstrate that the processing meets the requirements of Article 6(1), point (c) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, as well as Article 9(2), point (g) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.	Where special categories of personal data within the meaning of Article 9 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 are to be processed, the Digital Service Coordinator that grants the request should verify that the processing meets the requirements of Article 6(1), point (c) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, as well as Article 9(2), point (g) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
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Justification

Many datasets processed by very large online platforms and very large online search engines are likely to contain special categories of data within the meaning of Article 9 of the GDPR. Data providers would easily be able to block any meaningful access even after an access request is granted, by simply stating that the request is not “necessary for reasons of substantial public interest” as required under article 9(2), point (g) of the GDPR. Yet, if the DSC (Digital Services Coordinator) grants the request by a vetted researcher, it should be assumed that it meets the criterion set out by Article 40 (4) and (8), point (e), and is therefore “necessary for reasons of substantial public interest”. It is up to the DSC to ensure this.

- Article 2(4)

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
‘principal researcher’ means the applicant researcher who submits the data access application and assumes the responsibility for the completeness and accuracy of the information in and the supporting documentation of a data access application in their individual capacity or on behalf of an entity or a group of applicant researchers and acts as a contact point for the data access application when the vetted status is granted.	‘principal researcher’ means the applicant researcher who submits the data access application and assumes the responsibility for the completeness and accuracy of the information in and the supporting documentation of a data access application in their individual capacity or on behalf of an entity or a group of applicant researchers and acts as a contact point for the data access application when the vetted status is granted. Either a single individual or a group of individuals can be designated as ‘principal researcher’.

Justification:

The original text proposed by the Commission does not envisage plurality of principal researchers / principal investigators, which is quite common in research projects. Hence, we propose an expansion of the definition of ‘principal researchers’.

- Article 7

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>Formulation of reasoned request</p> <p>1. Within 5 working days from the receipt of the data access application, the Digital Services Coordinator to which the data access application has been submitted shall either confirm to the principal researcher that the application contains the information and supporting documentation listed in Article 8, or indicate which elements of the data access application require correction or completion, allowing the principal researcher to resubmit.</p> <p>2. Within 21 working days starting from the day after the confirmation of completeness of the data access application to the principal researcher, the Digital Service Coordinator of establishment shall:</p> <p>3.</p> <p>(a) Where appropriate, formulate a reasoned request, transmit it to the data provider and inform the principal researcher of its transmission;</p> <p>(b) or inform the principal researcher about the reasons why the reasoned request could not be formulated.</p> <p>Where, in duly justified cases, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment needs additional time to formulate the reasoned request, it may extend the deadline referred to in paragraph 2 for a reasonable period. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall notify the principal researcher of the extension and shall indicate the reasons for the delay and a new date for the transmission of the reasoned request to</p>	<p>Formulation of reasoned request</p> <p>1. Within 5 working days from the receipt of the data access application, the Digital Services Coordinator to which the data access application has been submitted shall either confirm to the principal researcher that the application contains the information and supporting documentation listed in Article 8, or indicate which elements of the data access application require correction or completion, allowing the principal researcher to resubmit.</p> <p>2. Within 21 working days starting from the day after the confirmation of completeness of the data access application to the principal researcher, the Digital Service Coordinator of establishment shall:</p> <p>3.</p> <p>(a) Where appropriate, formulate a reasoned request, transmit it to the data provider and inform the principal researcher of its transmission;</p> <p>(b) or inform the principal researcher about the reasons why the reasoned request could not be formulated; or</p> <p>(c) in cases where a principal researcher requires additional funding to provide documentation attesting to compliance with the conditions specified under Article 8(7) or Article 9(4) and where such additional funding relies on the outcome of an application to a funding organisation, the Digital Services Coordinator can issue a conditional reasoned request to the data provider and</p>

the data provider.	<p>issue a copy of such conditional reasoned request to the principal researcher.</p> <p>Where, in duly justified cases, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment needs additional time to formulate the reasoned request, it may extend the deadline referred to in paragraph 2 for 21 working days. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall notify the principal researcher of the extension and shall indicate the reasons for the delay and a new date for the transmission of the reasoned request to the data provider.</p>
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Justification

To enable a DSC to make a reasoned request, the principal researcher is required to provide proof of sufficient safeguards for confidentiality and data security. (Article 8(7)). The principal researcher is also required to provide proof of having obtained a secure processing environment, where required (Article 9(4)). The operator of such secure processing environment must provide documentation specifying the type of access controls to the environment, the type of logs that will be maintained, and a confirmation of the adequacy of the computing power made available to the requesting researchers. (Id.)

However, setting up and operating secure processing environments may require equipment and human resources that not all institutions to which principal researchers are affiliated have access to. Especially in the context of human and social sciences or in the context of lower-income EU member states, funding for such resources may depend entirely on the outcome of research grant applications or the core infrastructure of their host institution. In many cases, researchers often secure such computing environments by way of funding received from research agencies for a project. Such funders often take into account the feasibility of a project before making a decision on whether to fund a project. When a project is built around the analysis of data accessed through article 40(8) DSA, funding agencies may refuse projects that cannot prove the team is made up of vetted researchers who have had their data access application approved by a DSC. Indeed, confirmation that the DSC has issued a reasoned request would in such a scenario be a necessity to prove the feasibility of the project. As a result, we propose a mechanism by which DSCs can issue conditional reasoned requests, which can provide comfort to funders and thereby enable researchers to obtain the funding necessary to purchase a secure processing environment. Researchers can provide documentary evidence from the operator of such a secure processing environment on a later date, after which the actual data transfer from the data providers to the researchers through this environment can be undertaken.

- Article 8(1)

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the data access application includes the following elements: (1) the consent from the principal researcher to be the point of contact for the data access application;	The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the data access application includes the following elements: (1) the consent from each principal researcher to be the point of contact for the data access application;

Justification:

As mentioned above, it is common for research projects to be led by more than one principal researcher. We have proposed changes to account for this practice.

- Article 8(2)

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the data access application includes the following elements: (1) the consent from the principal researcher to be the point of contact for the data access application; (2) for each applicant researcher: (a) the identity and contact details of the applicant researcher; (b) documentary evidence of the existence of a formal relationship between the applicant researcher and the research organisation of affiliation; (c) confirmation of affiliation, independence from commercial interests and access to the technical means necessary to meet the requirements set out in Article 40(8), point (d), of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065;	The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the data access application includes the following elements: (1) the consent from the principal researcher to be the point of contact for the data access application; (2) for each applicant researcher: (a) the identity and contact details of the applicant researcher; (b) documentary evidence of the existence of a formal relationship between the applicant researcher and the research organisation of affiliation; (c) confirmation of affiliation, independence from commercial interests and access to the technical means necessary to meet the requirements set out in Article 40(8), point (d), of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065;

Justification

We propose deletion of the phrase ‘confirmation of affiliation’ as this would already be provided as part of documentary evidence on the existence of a formal relationship between the applicant researchers and research organisation of affiliation.

- Article 8(3)

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the data access application includes the following elements:</p> <p>(1) the consent from the principal researcher to be the point of contact for the data access application;</p> <p>(2) for each applicant researcher:</p> <p>(a) the identity and contact details of the applicant researcher;</p> <p>(b) documentary evidence of the existence of a formal relationship between the applicant researcher and the research organisation of affiliation;</p> <p>(c) confirmation of affiliation, independence from commercial interests and access to the technical means necessary to meet the requirements set out in Article 40(8), point (d), of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065;</p> <p>(3) information about funding, including both financial and non-financial contributions supporting the research project for which the data are requested;</p>	<p>The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the data access application includes the following elements:</p> <p>(1) the consent from the principal researcher to be the point of contact for the data access application;</p> <p>(2) for each applicant researcher:</p> <p>(a) the identity and contact details of the applicant researcher;</p> <p>(b) documentary evidence of the existence of a formal relationship between the applicant researcher and the research organisation of affiliation;</p> <p>(c) confirmation of affiliation, independence from commercial interests and access to the technical means necessary to meet the requirements set out in Article 40(8), point (d), of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065;</p> <p>(3) information about funding, including both financial and non-financial contributions supporting the research project for which the data are requested;</p>

Justification

Article 8(3) of the delegated act contains a contradiction: information on funding cannot contain non-financial elements. Further, and more importantly, the proposed specification of non-financial elements is contrary to Article 40(8)(c) of the Digital Services Act which states that when researchers seek the status of a ‘vetted researchers’, they must submit an application to the relevant DSC which “discloses the funding of the research.”

Article 290(1) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union states that the content of a delegation of power shall be explicitly defined in legislative acts. As a result, the Draft

Regulations should only specify provisions that conform to Article 40(8) of the Digital Services Act.

- Article 8

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the data access application includes the following elements:</p> <p>(7) the proposed safeguards to mitigate possible risks in terms of confidentiality, data security and personal data protection corresponding to the data requested, including as regards the modalities of access to and processing of the data;</p> <p>(8) an estimation of the required duration of the access, consistent with the described research activities and planned methodology;</p> <p>(9) a summary of the data access application insofar as it is relevant to the vetted status that has been granted, including the following elements:</p> <p>(a) an abstract of the research topic, including the systemic risks studied;</p> <p>(b) the data provider from which data are requested for the purposes of carrying out the research project;</p> <p>(c) a description of the data to be shared, including format, scope and, where possible, specific data points.</p>	<p>The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the data access application includes the following elements:</p> <p>(7) the proposed safeguards to mitigate possible risks in terms of confidentiality, data security and personal data protection corresponding to the data requested, including as regards the modalities of access to and processing of the data;</p> <p>(8) a copy of the data protection impact assessment undertaken, if so required under Article 35 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 ;</p> <p>(9) an estimation of the required duration of the access, consistent with the described research activities and planned methodology;</p> <p>(10) a summary of the data access application insofar as it is relevant to the vetted status that has been granted, including the following elements:</p> <p>(a) an abstract of the research topic, including the systemic risks studied;</p> <p>(b) the data provider from which data are requested for the purposes of carrying out the research project;</p> <p>(c) a description of the data to be shared, including format, scope and, where possible, specific data points.</p>

Justification

In addition to mitigating the data protection risks to *specific data subjects* whose personal data may form part of a *specific* data access request, it is also important to ensure researchers account for the risks of their proposed processing on the rights and freedoms of natural persons *more generally* - as data protections can manifest on a collective level as well. This may be

particularly relevant in cases where the shared data includes sensitive personal data as under Article 9 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679. As a result, where researchers are required to undertake a data protection impact assessment, such information should also be shared with DSCs to ensure holistic evaluation of the requesting researchers' ability to mitigate data protection and security risks.

- Article 9

Commission Proposal	Proposed Amendment
<p>4. Where, in accordance with the access modalities, a secure processing environment is used to grant access, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall require documentation attesting that the operator of that environment:</p> <p>(a) specifies access conditions to the secure processing environment in order to minimize the risk of the unauthorised reading, copying, modification or removal of the data hosted in the secure processing environment;</p> <p>(b) ensures that vetted researchers have access only to data covered by their reasoned request, by means of individual and unique user identities and confidential access modes;</p> <p>(c) keeps identifiable logs of access to the secure processing environment for the period necessary to verify and audit all processing operations in that environment;</p> <p>(d) ensures that the computing power at the disposal of the vetted researchers is appropriate and sufficient for the purposes of the research project;</p> <p>(e) monitors effectiveness of measures listed in points (a) to (d).</p>	<p>4. Where, in accordance with the access modalities, a secure processing environment is used to grant access, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall require documentation attesting that the operator of that environment:</p> <p>(a) specifies access conditions to the secure processing environment in order to minimize the risk of the unauthorised reading, copying, modification or removal of the data hosted in the secure processing environment;</p> <p>(b) ensures that vetted researchers have access only to data covered by their reasoned request, by means of individual and unique user identities and confidential access modes;</p> <p>(c) keeps identifiable logs of access to the secure processing environment for the period necessary to verify and audit all processing operations in that environment;</p> <p>(d) ensures that the computing power at the disposal of the vetted researchers is appropriate and sufficient for the purposes of the research project;</p> <p>(e) monitors effectiveness of measures listed in points (a) to (d).</p> <p>5. In cases where a principal researcher requires additional funding to provide documentation attesting to compliance with the conditions specified under Article 9(4) and where such additional funding is typically confirmed by the funding organisation after issuance of a reasoned</p>

	<p>request, the principal researcher can provide alternate documentation specifying the following:</p> <p>(i) an explanation of the funding required to obtain a secure processing environment,;</p> <p>(ii) a promise to ensure compliance with the conditions specified in Article 9(4) upon issuance of the reasoned request and upon receipt of funding from the funding organisation to purchase secure processing environments; and</p> <p>(iii) an indicative list of proposed operators of secure processing environments.</p> <p>Within 21 days of acceptance by the data provider of a reasoned request issued by the Digital Services Coordinator, the principal researcher shall obtain documentation from the operator of a secure processing environment attesting to compliance with the conditions specified in Article 9(4) and shall submit such documentation to the Digital Services Coordinator.</p>
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Justification:

Not all researchers may have secure processing environments in place before making a data access request to the DSCs. In many cases, researchers often secure such computing environments by way of funding received from donors for a project. It is also likely that donors will require confirmation that the DSC has issued a reasoned request, **before** making funds available for the purchase of a secure processing environment.

As a result, we propose a mechanism by which DSCs can issue conditional reasoned requests, which can provide comfort to funders and thereby enable researchers to obtain the funding necessary to purchase a secure processing environment. In such cases, we propose an alternate list of documents that can be provided by the principal researcher at the initial stage of making a data request, and additional documents by the operator of a secure processing environment to show compliance with Article 9(4) can be provided on a later date (after issuance of a reasoned request by the DSC).

- Article 10

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>1. The reasoned request shall contain at least the following elements:</p> <p>(a) the contact details of the principal researcher;</p> <p>(b) the date by which the data provider shall give access to the data requested and the date on which such access shall be terminated;</p> <p>(c) the access modalities for the sharing of the data with the vetted researchers;</p> <p>(d) the summary of the data access application referred to in Article 8, point (i).</p> <p>2. The names and contact details of all vetted researchers mentioned in the data access application may be disclosed where this is necessary to enable access to the data, in accordance with the access modalities specified in the reasoned request.</p>	<p>1. The reasoned request shall contain at least the following elements:</p> <p>(a) the contact details of the principal researcher;</p> <p>(b) the date by which the data provider shall give access to the data requested and the date on which such access shall be terminated;</p> <p>(c) the access modalities for the sharing of the data with the vetted researchers;</p> <p>(d) the summary of the data access application referred to in Article 8, point (i).</p> <p>2. The names and contact details of all vetted researchers mentioned in the data access application may be disclosed where this is necessary to enable access to the data, in accordance with the access modalities specified in the reasoned request.</p> <p>3. Any change in the principal researcher during the subsistence of a reasoned request or during the subsistence of a data access period shall be communicated to the Digital Services Coordinator of the place of establishment within a reasonable period.</p>

Justification:

Change of principal researchers during the subsistence of a project is a common occurrence. The change proposed here is intended to ensure transparency, by obliging principal researchers to communicate any change to the DSC within a reasonable period of time.

- Article 10(2)

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>1. The reasoned request shall contain at least the following elements:</p> <p>(a) the contact details of the principal researcher;</p> <p>(b) the date by which the data provider shall give access to the data requested and</p>	<p>1. The reasoned request shall contain at least the following elements:</p> <p>(a) the contact details of the principal researcher;</p> <p>(b) the date by which the data provider shall give access to the data requested and</p>

<p>the date on which such access shall be terminated;</p> <p>(c) the access modalities for the sharing of the data with the vetted researchers;</p> <p>(d) the summary of the data access application referred to in Article 8, point (i).</p> <p>2. The names and contact details of all vetted researchers mentioned in the data access application may be disclosed where this is necessary to enable access to the data, in accordance with the access modalities specified in the reasoned request.</p>	<p>the date on which such access shall be terminated;</p> <p>(c) the access modalities for the sharing of the data with the vetted researchers;</p> <p>(d) the summary of the data access application referred to in Article 8, point (i).</p> <p>2. The names and contact details of all vetted researchers mentioned in the data access application may be disclosed to the public on the DSA data access portal where this is necessary to enable access to the data, in accordance with the access modalities specified in the reasoned request.</p>
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Justification:

Article 10(2) should specify to whom personal data of researchers will be disclosed. We have proposed changes on the assumption that such disclosure will be made to the public, by way of the DSA data access portal. If disclosures are to be made to other third parties, the same should also be specified in this provision.

- Article 13

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>Dispute settlement procedure</p> <p>1. If the data provider disagrees with the decision of the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment following an amendment request, the data provider may ask the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment to participate in a mediation. The request for mediation shall include the identity and contact details of the proposed mediator.</p> <p>2. The mediator shall be impartial and independent. The objective of the mediator shall be to help parties reach an agreement that:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> allows vetted researchers to access the data protects the rights and interests of the data provider 	<p>Dispute settlement procedure</p> <p>1. If the data provider disagrees with the decision of the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment following an amendment request, the data provider may ask the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment to participate in a mediation. The request for mediation shall include the identity and contact details of the proposed mediator.</p> <p>2. The mediator shall be impartial and meet the same independence criteria as those set forth under article 40 (8) of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065. The mediator shall also possess relevant academic qualifications, scientific experience, expertise, and proven</p>

<p>and the vetted researchers.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the mediator proposed meets the requirements of impartiality and independence and has qualified and relevant experience in relation to the elements laid down in Article 40(5) of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 and is able to act without undue delay. If the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment determines that the proposed mediator does not meet those requirements, it may ask the data provider to propose another mediator. When the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment has verified that the proposed mediator meets those requirements, it shall confirm the suitability of the mediator. 4. The data provider shall be solely responsible for covering the costs of the mediation. 5. Where appropriate, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment may invite the principal researcher to join the mediation as a party to help reach an agreement that supports the objectives of the research project in relation to which the data was requested. 6. The data provider, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment and, where relevant, the principal researcher, shall act in good faith throughout the mediation. 7. The participation in mediation shall not affect the rights of the parties to initiate judicial proceedings at any time before, during or after the mediation. 8. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment may set a time limit for the mediation, which cannot exceed two months from the date on which the meditation process was started in accordance with paragraph 1. If no 	<p>skills related to the scientific disciplines and methods used in the research project described in the data access application. The objective of the mediator shall be to help parties reach an agreement that:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. allows vetted researchers to access the data b. protects the rights and interests of the data provider and the vetted researchers. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall verify that the mediator proposed meets the requirements of impartiality and independence and has qualified and relevant experience in relation to the elements laid down in Article 40(5) of Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 and is able to act without undue delay. If the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment determines that the proposed mediator does not meet those requirements, it may ask the data provider to propose another mediator. When the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment has verified that the proposed mediator meets those requirements, it shall confirm the suitability of the mediator. 4. The data provider shall be solely responsible for covering the costs of the mediation. 5. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall always invite the principal researcher to join the mediation as a party to help reach an agreement that supports the objectives of the research project in relation to which the data was requested. 6. The data provider, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment and, where relevant, the principal researcher, shall act in good faith throughout the mediation. 7. The participation in mediation shall
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<p>agreement has been reached within that time limit, the mediator shall declare the mediation closed.</p> <p>9. The mediator may end the mediation earlier if:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. one of the parties requests it explicitly; b. it becomes clear that the parties' conduct during the mediation makes it c. unlikely that an agreement will be reached. <p>10. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall register in AGORA a summary record of the mediation, prepared by the mediator and signed by all parties. The record shall include the following information:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. the date of the request for mediation by the data provider; b. the identities and contact details of the participants; c. the start and end dates of the mediation; d. the outcome of the mediation, including any agreement reached or the reason e. for termination of the mediation. <p>11. Where the mediation leads to an agreement resulting in granting access to the data on terms that are different to those specified in the reasoned request, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall amend the reasoned request to reflect that agreement.</p>	<p>not affect the rights of the parties to initiate judicial proceedings at any time before, during or after the mediation.</p> <p>8. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment may set a time limit for the mediation, which cannot exceed two months from the date on which the mediation process was started in accordance with paragraph 1. If no agreement has been reached within that time limit, the mediator shall declare the mediation closed.</p> <p>9. The mediator may end the mediation earlier if:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. one of the parties requests it explicitly; b. it becomes clear that the parties' conduct during the mediation makes it c. unlikely that an agreement will be reached. <p>10. The Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall register in AGORA a summary record of the mediation, prepared by the mediator and signed by all parties. The record shall include the following information:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. the date of the request for mediation by the data provider; b. the identities and contact details of the participants; c. the start and end dates of the mediation; d. the outcome of the mediation, including any agreement reached or the reason e. for termination of the mediation. <p>11. Where the mediation leads to an agreement resulting in granting access to the data on terms that are different to those specified in the reasoned request, the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment shall amend the reasoned request to reflect that agreement.</p>
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Justification:

The mediator must possess relevant academic and scientific qualifications, to ensure a fair adjudication of the dispute. His independence must also be proven, especially to ensure that this process is compliant with article 13 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. Indeed, not being specific enough about who could act as a mediator may lead to a situation where administrative authorities or persons that are tied to commercial interests exercise control over the agenda of public interest research. This would be contrary to the principle of academic freedom. It is also very important to ensure that mediators have the necessary and relevant knowledge in the specialised scientific field of the principal investigator(s) to be able to understand the content of the application for a reasoned request.

Further, the principal researcher must always be invited to the mediation, to ensure that principles of due process are observed.

- Article 14

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>Independent advisory mechanisms</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Before formulating a reasoned request, or taking a decision on an amendment request, the Digital Services Coordinator may decide to consult experts.2. The experts shall:<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. be independent and impartial;b. possess relevant expertise and proven skills and have the capacity and resources to perform the identified task, without incurring undue delay.3. To attest impartiality, the experts shall sign a declaration confirming that they:<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. have no financial or personal ties to the data provider or the applicant researchers;b. have no interest in the outcome of the data access process;c. are free from any conflicts of interest.	<p>Independent advisory mechanisms</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Before formulating a reasoned request, or taking a decision on an amendment request, the Digital Services Coordinator may decide to consult experts.2. The experts shall:<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. be independent and impartial;b. possess relevant academic and scientific experience, expertise and proven skills related to the scientific disciplines and methods used in the research project described in the data access application and have the capacity and resources to perform the identified task, without incurring undue delay.3. To attest impartiality, the experts shall sign a declaration confirming that they:<ol style="list-style-type: none">a. have no financial or personal ties to the data provider or the

<p>4. The Digital Services Coordinator shall encode any consultation carried out pursuant to paragraph 1, along with the expert opinion received in response to the consultation, without undue delay in AGORA.</p> <p>5. Prior to initiating new consultations, the Digital Services Coordinators are encouraged to refer to previous outcomes.</p>	<p>applicant researchers;</p> <p>b. have no interest in the outcome of the data access process;</p> <p>c. are free from any conflicts of interest.</p> <p>4. The Digital Services Coordinator shall encode any consultation carried out pursuant to paragraph 1, along with the expert opinion received in response to the consultation, without undue delay in AGORA.</p> <p>5. Prior to initiating new consultations, the Digital Services Coordinators are encouraged to refer to previous outcomes.</p>
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Justification

This precision is necessary to ensure that the process respects academic freedom, as laid out under article 13 of the Charter, and that the experts do have the expertise over the relevant fields to assess the application for reasoned requests submitted to their review. As it stands, the Commission’s proposal appears to assume that anyone can understand any such application, regardless of the field and scientific discipline at hand. Such an assumption would be wrong.

- Article 15

Commission Proposal	Proposed amendment
<p>1. Data providers shall notify the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment within 24 hours:</p> <p>(a) that the vetted researchers have access to the data requested, in accordance with the access modalities specified in the reasoned request;</p> <p>(b) that the access for the vetted researchers is terminated.</p> <p>2. Data providers shall provide vetted researchers with relevant documentation related to the data requested. In cases where the provision of such documentation results in a significant vulnerability, the data provider shall notify the Digital Services</p>	<p>1. Data providers shall notify the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment within 24 hours of receipt of a reasoned request from the Digital Services Coordinator:</p> <p>(a) that the vetted researchers have access to the data requested, in accordance with the access modalities specified in the reasoned request;</p> <p>(b) that the access for the vetted researchers is terminated.</p> <p>2. Data providers shall provide vetted researchers with access to all relevant data falling into the scope of the reasoned request, including relevant documentation related to the data requested. In cases</p>

<p>Coordinator of establishment and, where possible, propose alternative documentation.</p> <p>3. When providing access to data, data providers shall not impose archiving, storage, refresh and deletion requirements that hinder the research referred to in the reasoned request in any way.</p> <p>4. Data providers shall be allowed to limit vetted researchers' use of standard analytical tools, including relevant software libraries, for the analysis of the data requested, only if it is specified in the reasoned request.</p>	<p>where the provision of such documentation results in a significant vulnerability, the data provider shall notify the Digital Services Coordinator of establishment and, where possible, propose alternative documentation.</p> <p>3. When providing access to data, data providers shall not impose archiving, storage, refresh and deletion requirements that hinder the research referred to in the reasoned request in any way.</p> <p>4. Data providers shall be allowed to limit vetted researchers' use of standard analytical tools, including relevant software libraries, for the analysis of the data requested, only if it is specified in the reasoned request.</p>
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Justification:

We have proposed an amendment to clarify the time period within which data providers must respond to a reasoned request.

We also propose clarifying the fact that documentation falls under the scope of “data” to avoid creating a distinction between “data” and “documentation” or giving the impression that this provision goes beyond that is provided for in the DSA.

Finally, once a reasoned request has been granted, data providers should no longer be able to object to providing access to data, including documentation. If such a risk arises, it must be raised during the assessment made by the DSC before the reasoned request is granted. It must also be noted that nothing the DSA appears to suggest that the legislator aimed at allowing VLOPs or VLOSEs to oppose reasoned requests once granted, except by challenging the decision before the relevant courts.

Concluding remarks

In addition to specific amendments to the Draft Regulations, we would also like to offer some general remarks in relation to the data access framework contained within Article 40 of the DSA.

- Article 40(8) of the DSA lays down the definition of a “vetted researcher”, which includes the condition that such researcher must be “independent from commercial interests.” This strict definition excludes certain classes of researchers. For instance, there is a PhD funding scheme known as CIFRE or “Industrial Agreements for Training through Research” in France. Under this scheme, companies registered under French law can recruit a doctoral student whose research project, conducted in collaboration with a public laboratory affiliated to a University doctoral school, will lead to the defence of a PhD thesis. CIFRE working contracts and related expenses environment are co-funded by the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation and the company. Doctoral researchers under CIFRE agreements would be excluded from Article 40(8) and Article 40(12), but the commercial entity is not likely to have any control over the research project for which data access is sought. Similarly, collaborations within EU funded projects consortia often include a commercial entity as partner. To the extent such projects are excluded from Article 40(8), it is important to continue to ensure the availability of public funds and non-profit funding options for researchers.
- At present, neither Article 40 of the DSA nor other provisions require that research outputs culminating from access to data under Article 40 be published under open access arrangements. A commitment to open science is important, to ensure transparency and prevent misuse of Article 40(8) and Article 40(12) for commercial exploitation. At the same time, openly licensed works / open access publications can also be exploited. We take note the definition of “research organisations” in Article 2(1) of Directive 2019/790, referred to in Article 40(8), which excludes organisations undertake scientific research outputs “in such a way that the access to the results generated by such scientific research cannot be enjoyed on a preferential basis by an undertaking that exercises a decisive influence upon such organisation.” We hope increased use of Article 40(8) by researchers also encourages more open discussion among researchers and funding organisations on different publication and dissemination options for research outputs.

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